

ROLE OF HEALTHY LIFESTYLE, YOGA IN WELLNESS

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Abstract:

Study was individual's Yoga experience as it relates to psychological wellness, physical wellness, and subjective well-being. Men and women, Yoga participants, as compared to non-Yoga participants, were more likely to perceive higher levels of perceived wellness, in almost all domains tested, than exercisers versus no exercisers. The results of this study bring merit to Yoga participants' perception of wellness. This research is significant as it validates the role Yoga plays in the health and well-being of participants.

Key Words: Yoga, Wellness, Well-Being, Quantitative, Observational, Life Satisfaction, Mindfulness & Survey

In today's world health scenario there are many factors driving the growth of diseases, but most experts agree that changes in lifestyle and diet are the major attributes. As developing countries rapidly industrialize, people tend to do work involving less physical activity. At the same time, the availability of food that is cheap but high in calories becomes more common. Stress and other psychological phenomena also play a key role in widespread illnesses. The trend emerging is that the age ranges have been dropping, so that people are getting sick in the prime of their life.

The word 'cure' has been removed from the dictionary of the medical world! Medical professionals base their practice on this concept which can present frustration and a dilemma to patients who want to cure or full recovery from their disease.

In Yoga, 'Cure' is possible due to the treatment of the root cause of the disease. Through Yoga emotional imbalances are brought down by the art of sublimation of emotions. They eradicate the root cause of the diseases, Ādhi. Advanced yogic techniques harness energy to bring about powerful healing of dreaded diseases like Cancer.

Yoga offers solutions as it is multi-dimensional; hence can offer a total solution. It is here that India has to make its great contributions, as India has the complete knowledge base, which is contained in the Vedas. Coming from the root vid jnane, the Vedas treasure us with the total knowledge - a knowledge-base much needed for us in the modern era to meet the challenge.

Derived from the verbal root Yuj, the term yoga means joining; joining our small individual personality with all pervasive cosmic personality; raising us from an animalistic level to the highest levels of perfection, featured by total freedom, knowledge and bliss as shown below.

Yoga as is commonly understood is not merely practices at the body, breath or mind levels. Yoga is a lifestyle where we are able to live without any conflict, in a state of harmony with ourselves and with others around us. Yoga offers total freedom, total power, total knowledge and total bliss!

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